

Effect of Cationic and Anionic Surfactants on the Reaction of Sodium Sulphite and Benzyl Chloride†

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The kinetics of the reaction of benzyl chloride with sodium sulphite have been studied in the presence of varying concentration of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS) in DMF-water mixtures at 35° and in 40 : 60 (v/v) DMF-water, methanol-water mixtures at 30°, respectively. The reaction follows total second order kinetics and the second order rate constants increases with increasing concentration of CTAB but decreases with increasing concentration of NaLS. The effect of solvent composition and alkali metal salts on the reaction rate in presence of CTAB has been studied. The observations have been discussed. The CMC values of surfactants have been determined in mixed solvent system.

A close review of literature indicates that aliphatic nucleophilic substitution reactions in the presence of surfactants have not been studied vividly. Bunton *et al.*¹ have studied some of them. We have also published a number of papers²⁻⁵ using carboxylate ions and thiosulphate ion as nucleophiles. In the present work the reaction of sulphite ion has been examined in the presence of surfactants in order to gather additional informations to the field of kinetics in micellar phase.

Experimental

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and sodium lauryl sulphate (both B.D.H., England) were purified by the methods available in literature⁶. Benzyl chloride (B.D.H.) was distilled before use. Sodium sulphite (A.R., B.D.H.) was used without further purification. Methanol and dimethylformamide were purified by standard methods. Triple-distilled water was used for dilution. The alkali metal salts were of A.R. grade and dried to constant weight before use.

Kinetic measurements : Benzyl chloride (0.025 M, 20 ml) in dimethylformamide and aqueous solution of surfactant of appropriate concentrations were taken in a glass stoppered conical flask, and sodium sulphite solution in water of known concentration (0.05 M) in another stoppered container were preheated in a thermostatic bath in order to attain the desired temperature. Then sodium sulphite solution (0.05 M, 20 ml) was pipetted out and transferred to the stoppered conical flask. The total volume of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 50 ml. Thus, the concentrations of the nucleophile and substrate become 0.02 and 0.01 M, respectively.

The reaction was followed by quenching 5 ml of the reaction mixture at an interval of 10 min in

conical flask containing 15 ml of 0.01 M iodine solution. Then it was acidified with 5 ml of 2 N HCl and diluted with 10-20 ml distilled water. The unreacted sulphite consumes iodine in accordance with the equation,

and the unreacted excess iodine was estimated by titrating against 0.02 M thiosulphate using starch as an indicator⁷. In order to fix various solvent composition and keep salts of particular concentration in the reaction mixture, required adjustments were done keeping the total volume of reaction mixture fixed at 50 ml. To prevent aerial oxidation of SO_3^{2-} , 0.1% of EDTA concentration was maintained in the reaction mixture⁸. The rate data were computed graphically from the plot of $\log(a-x)/(b-x)$ against time (t) using the expression,

$$k_2 = \frac{2.303}{a-b} \times \text{slope}$$

where (a-x) and (b-x) are the concentrations of benzyl chloride and sodium sulphite, respectively in the reaction mixture after a time interval t. All the rate constants are accurate within $\pm 2\%$ for duplicate determinations.

CMC determination : The CMC of CTAB and NaLS have been determined by the measurement of specific conductivity⁹ using a Toshniwal CL-0106 conductivity analyser.

Results and Discussion

The critical micelle concentration (CMC) of CTAB and NaLS have been determined in aquo-organic medium by many workers. Shinoda *et al.*¹⁰ have reported that the CMC of CTAB and NaLS decreased by addition of ethanol and other organic

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solvents to water. But the CMC of DTAB has been found to increase in methanol-water than in water¹¹. In case of CTAB the CMC increase has also been observed¹² in DMF-water mixture. So it is evident that the CMCs of ionic surfactant increase in methanol-water and DMF-water mixture. For further confirmation the CMC of CTAB and NaLS have been determined in pure water and 40 : 60 v/v methanol-water by us. It was seen that the CMC values increased in methanol-water. The values for CTAB and NaLS in pure water were found to be 9.2×10^{-4} and $7.7 \times 10^{-3} M$, respectively and those in methanol-water were 1.6×10^{-3} and $14.8 \times 10^{-3} M$, respectively at 35°. These values have been taken into account in this kinetic study.

Effect of solvent compositions and solvents : The kinetics of the reaction have been followed in DMF-water (40 : 60, v/v) in presence of varying concentration of CTAB and in methanol-water and DMF-water (40 : 60, v/v) in presence of varying concentration of NaLS. The rate of reaction is found to increase with increasing dielectric constant of the medium in the absence and as well as in the presence of 0.03M CTAB (Table 3). The same phenomena have been observed^{6,15} in case of benzyl chloride and thiosulphate reaction. The plots of $\log k_2$ vs $1/D$ are found to be linear. The k_2 values are greater in case of solvent having higher percentage of water. It indicates that the transition state is more polar than the reactant state¹⁶ and this may

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR REACTION OF BENZYL CHLORIDE WITH SODIUM SULPHITE IN PRESENCE OF CTAB IN DMF-WATER 40 : 60 (v/v) AT 35°

[CTAB] in M	[Benzyl chloride] = 0.01 M,				[Sodium sulphite] = 0.02 M			
	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07
$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	1.12	1.56	1.86	2.17	2.49	2.74	3.03	2.67

TABLE 2—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR REACTION OF BENZYL CHLORIDE WITH SODIUM SULPHITE IN PRESENCE OF NaLS IN AQUO-ORGANIC SOLVENTS (40 : 60, v/v) AT 30°

[NaLS] in M	[Benzyl chloride] = 0.01 M,				[Sodium sulphite] = 0.02 M			
	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	
	Methanol-water							
$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)*	1.30 (1.84)	1.16 (1.72)	0.90 (1.63)	0.75 (1.47)	0.72 (1.36)	0.69 (1.29)	0.64 (1.19)	
	DMF-water							
$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	1.00	0.85	0.74	0.62	0.56	0.54	0.51	

* Values in parentheses from Ref. 5 for thiosulphate nucleophile under similar experimental condition.

Effect of surfactant : The effect of varying concentration of CTAB and NaLS above their CMC upon the second order rate constant (k_2) for the reaction between benzyl chloride and sodium sulphite has been studied in DMF-water and methanol-water at different temperatures (Tables 1 and 2).

The rate of reaction increases with the increase of [CTAB] and it decreases with the increase of [NaLS] upto 0.06 M in both the cases. This behaviour is in accordance with the micellar catalysis of organic reactions of anion-neutral molecule type¹³. With increasing concentration of CTAB the relative concentrations of organic substrate and ionic reactant in the Stern layer of the micelle increases rapidly. This tends to accelerate the reaction. Beyond 0.06 M CTAB the k_2 value decreased.

The inhibition by NaLS may be due to increasing concentrations of unreactive counter-ions and increasing affinity of unreactive counter-ions for the Stern layer. Since there is possibility of competition between reactive and unreactive ions for sites in the Stern layer, the rate of reaction decreases¹⁴. The observations above 0.07 CTAB and 0.06M NaLS in the reaction mixture could not be recorded due to solubility problem.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION UPON CTAB CATALYSED REACTION OF BENZYL CHLORIDE AND SODIUM SULPHITE

Solven composition DMF-water (v/v)	[Benzyl chloride] = 0.01 M, [Sodium sulphite] = 0.02 M, Temp. = 35°	
	CTAB in M	
	0.00	0.03
	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	
30 : 70	3.84	4.45
35 : 65	2.24	3.31
40 : 60	1.125	2.17

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENTS AND TEMPERATURES UPON REACTION OF BENZYL CHLORIDE AND SODIUM SULPHITE

Solvent composition 40 : 60 (v/v)	[Benzyl chloride] = 0.01 M, [Sodium sulphite] = 0.02 M				$\Delta E^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ at 30 e.u.	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹
	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)		$\Delta E^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ at 30 e.u.			
	30°	35°					
Methanol-water	1.32	1.51	1.70	5.02	-51.00	20.47	
DMF-water	1.02	1.125	1.30	5.53	-49.75	20.60	

also be due to the formation of aggregates of surfactant of higher number¹⁰. Further, the rate of the reaction has been measured in 40 : 60 (v/v) DMF-water and methanol-water mixtures at three different temperatures in the absence of CTAB

(Table 4). It is seen that the rate constants are greater in methanol-water mixture. In an ion neutral molecule reaction the rate will be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant. It is known that dielectric constant of methanol-water is lower than that of DMF-water for a fixed composition. So these observations are in accordance with Ingold rule¹⁷.

In the absence and presence of varying concentrations of NaLS the rate of reaction has been measured in methanol-water and DMF-water (40 : 60, v/v) (Table 2). It is observed that the rate constant is greater in methanol-water than in DMF-water as per the Ingold rule. However, in presence of CTAB observations in varying composition of DMF-water are not in agreement with the Ingold rule. This may be due to the effect of CTAB and solvent composition on the ionic radius which varies in different environment¹⁸ and responsible for rate.

Effect of temperature : The rate of reaction increases with the increase in temperature. The thermodynamic parameters have been calculated (Table 4 and 5) using Arrhenius plot and Eyrings

TABLE 5—RATE CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND VARIATION OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR REACTION BETWEEN BENZYL CHLORIDE AND SODIUM SULPHITE IN PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS IN 40% METHANOL (v/v)

[Benzyl chloride] = 0.01 M, [Sodium sulphite] = 0.02 M, [Surfactant] = 0.03 M						
10 ³ k ₂ in dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ at			ΔE [‡]	ΔS [‡] at	ΔG [‡]	
30°	35°	40°	kcal mol ⁻¹	30° e.u.	kcal mol ⁻¹	
CTAB						
2.35	4.08	6.75	19.26	-2.43	18.52	
NaLS						
0.75	1.02	1.50	13.89	-22.76	7.00	

equation. The activation energy for the reaction in absence of surfactant is higher in DMF-water system than that of methanol-water. This indicates that the reactant is more solvated in DMF-water than the activated complex in comparison to methanol-water system. The high negative entropy indicates the greater compactness in ground state. However, in presence of surfactants the reactions proceeded with a higher activation energy and the entropy values were negative. The free energy of activation values are comparable except in presence of NaLS.

Effect of salts in presence of CTAB : The reaction has been studied in presence of 0.03 M CTAB by adding 0.02 M sulphates of alkali metals. The k₂ values have been tabulated in Table 6. It is observed that addition of these salts inhibit the catalysis by CTAB to the same extent. The inhibition is not very significant. The variation of cation sizes do not produce any effect on rate.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF SALTS ON RATE OF REACTION BETWEEN BENZYL CHLORIDE AND SODIUM SULPHITE IN PRESENCE OF CTAB IN DMF-WATER (40 : 60, v/v) AT 35°

[Benzyl chloride] = 0.01 M, [Sodium sulphite] = 0.02 M, [Salt] = 0.02 M, [CTAB] = 0.0 M	
Salt	10 ³ k ₂ in dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Li ₂ SO ₄	1.94
Na ₂ SO ₄	1.91
K ₂ SO ₄	1.85

It is also concluded that the rate constant (k₂) for the reaction between benzyl chloride and sulphite nucleophile is less than that with thiosulphate as nucleophile in presence of varying concentration of surfactant (Table 2). The nucleophilic constant values¹⁸ of sulphite and thiosulphate ions are 5.1 and 6.36, respectively which are in good agreement with the kinetic result.

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